

D3.5

EMPOWER

deliverables

Deliverable name

FULL SYSTEM DESIGN DOCUMENT

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System components needed to get eye-tracking data from devices to be used as an input for the platform games, as well as interfaces with WP4.

Description

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Work Package. 3

Lead Beneficiary – (UV)

FULL SYSTEM DESIGN DOCUMENT

Executive Summary

This deliverable reflects in detail the overall architecture of the platform and the detailed design of every single component of the platform.

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#1. Introduction

In this deliverable we describe all the elements contained in the project's main platform. This platform contains the main application for the project, including the nine games developed for children with neurodevelopmental disorders (NDDs), the wearable and eye tracker, and the local database to store all the data needed from the games. These games are based on two important constructs: **Executive Functions (EFs)** and **Emotion Regulation (ER)** intervention strategies. Specifically, we have five games to work on Executive Functions and four games to work on Emotion Regulation strategies.

In previous deliverables (3.3. and 3.4), we have described the state of the platform, each of the games to work on executive functions, and the features and abilities of the platform.

In this deliverable, we will focus more on the technical part, describing all the components included in the platform, the class diagram for each module, the database structure and specification, the user interface of the application and all the functionality contained inside the platform.

#2. Complete platform diagram

Before describing each of the platform's components, we would like to show a global diagram where it is possible to see all the modules and the inter-relation among them.

As can be seen in the diagram, we have several important elements inside the platform. Let's summarise the objective of each of them and then go on to describe each one in detail:

- a. **Main application:** This application contains all the components needed to play the games included in the platform. For that purpose, this application contains:
 - i. **A User Interface:** this is an important part of the application that allows the user to navigate through all the resources and content of the game.
 - ii. **Map:** in this case, this element is part of the interface, which allows you to select the game you would like to play at each moment.
 - iii. **Game module:** it is responsible for each of the games created. To control and implement the games, we have a general class containing all the common elements for the games. From this base class, each game derives to implement the specific functionalities and contents. Inside the game module, we have:
 1. **Data recorder for Replay:** this component is a massive data collector to allow, not only the replay of each game as it was played in a session, but also to extract all the necessary data for the algorithms to make decisions.
 2. **Eye tracking Module (ET):** this component is included in some games (depending on the interaction characteristics) to allow the application to control where the user is looking while playing with the games.
- b. **Wearable Module:** this is an external component from the main application because it is an application installed in the wearable used to record the physiological answer of each student while playing the games. This module has two main parts:
 - i. A user interface designed for the watch, that provides necessary support for connecting the wearable with the platform and configuring basic information about the participant
 - ii. A service module that collects the data from the sensors in real time and transmits the information to the platform
- c. **Teacher application:** this is an external application which helps the teacher not only to answer some parts of the questionnaires needed for the research but also, to control different elements during the session:
 - the state of the devices (ET and Wearable) during the sessions
 - give feedback in real-time about the emotional state of the child
 - give feedback in real-time about the specific behaviour that the child can show
 - report in real-time events that can happen during the session.
- d. **MariaDB Database (DB):** this is a local database installed inside each computer used to play the games. The platform records in this DB all the data needed for later analysis (wearable and ET data, games data, real-time events data...).
- e. **Local storage:** this is local data that some modules can generate and record internally in the computer where the games are played. Most of them are json data to allow the researchers to reproduce exactly the games after the session is finished.

In the following table we can see the availability of the eye-tracker and wearable in each game:

Game	Eye-tracker	Wearable
Mushroom hunter (attention)		
WorM (working memory)		
ReStroop (inhibition)		
ReFlex (Cognitive Flexibility)		
BEeHOLD (Delayed gratification)		
Wheel game (emotion game)		
CornHole game (emotion game)		
Egg pyramid (emotion game)		

Let's review each part in detail.

#3. Main application

This application is the container for all the games included in the project, the interface to create users and students and control the performance and improvement of each child, and the eye-tracking to control where the child is looking in each moment while playing a game. It is an application that can be used only in Windows because of the Eye Tracker device limitations. To use it, you only need to install the Tobii Pro Nano driver on Windows and the corresponding version for Node.JS and MariaDB database, to store all the data inside the local database. In Annex 1, it is possible to see the manual to get the main application ready to play.

USER INTERFACE AND MAP

The user interface of the main application is the general interface, allowing the user to create accounts and navigate between and inside the games. It is divided into two parts: the general interface and the game interface. The general interface is common for the whole application and has the main purpose of navigating and giving access to each game. The game interface is more specific and includes general elements common for all the games and specific elements which are different for each game (due to the different objectives, interaction methods and functionality).

MAIN INTERFACE

This main interface starts with an initial animation introducing the concept of Eco Farm and the environment where all the games will take place.

After that, a login screen is shown to allow the user to register or to use his/her username and password to enter the application. This registration is local, the user creates a profile inside the local database installed in the computer used to play.

If a profile is created, you only need your username and password to access the application. If you do not have any profile created, the registration is very easy because the application asks only for a username (an email address) and a password. We do not store any other information about the user (in this case, the teacher, family member or professional working with the child).

After logging in, the user can review his/her student list and select one of them to play the games.

If the user needs to create a new student, there is a button to access a new part of the interface to allow the creation of new students. For that, the application asks for:

- nickname
- the year of birth
- sex
- medication (yes/no, which)
- conditions (selection among a list of conditions)
- hand to wear the wearable

When you Add the student, you will return to the student list, and you can select the child who is going to play the games in that session. After selecting the student, the application shows a map with all the areas included in the farm. In each area, you can play a game related to a specific construct in the executive functions or emotional regulation. In this stage of the project, we have five games developed (in this case, those of Executive Functions) and four more under development. In the current stage of the map, it is possible to see the six different games currently ready to play (Attention game, Inhibition game, Working Memory game, Cognitive Flexibility game, Delayed Gratification game and the first version of Emotion Naming). Each one is assigned to a specific area of the farm.

Also, in this map screen, it is possible to access the information of the student selected, to allow the user (teacher/professional) to check specific information about the child playing at that moment.

When a specific button inside the map is selected, we enter that area to play the game associated with it.

For this part of the main application, the flowchart is:

And the UML diagram of classes is: (see more detailed diagram in Annex 2 and Annex 5 for bigger size)

General class diagram part 1

Class diagram in detail part 1

All the elements which need connection with the server and database, use the HTTPRequest class. The attribute in the class is a Unity GameObject, and inside the code, we access to the HTTPRequest script that the gameobject has attached:

General class diagram part 2

Class diagram in detail part 2

Class	Description
PersistentData	Class to control all the variables shared by different classes and scenes that need to persist along the application.
User	It is the teacher or professional who helps the children to enter the application, selects the games to play and controls the child interaction during the session.
Student	It is the child with neurodevelopmental disorders who plays the games.
Session	It is the collection of games or activities the child will play in a specific day and moment.
Activity	It is each of the games from the platform.
ActivityType	It is an enumeration with the types of activities.
ConditionType	It is an enumeration with a list of possible conditions for the child profile.
InterfaceCtrl	It is the main class to control all the interaction and screen changes inside the application interface.
LoginCtrl	It is a class to read and access to the user through his/her username and password.
RegisterCtrl	It is the class to allow the registration of new users.
ErrorPanelCtrl	It is a class to help the other part of the application to keep the user informed about possible errors or problems while interacting with the interface.
AddStudentCtrl	It is a class to allow the creation of new students associated with a specific user.
SetRandomIconData	It is a class to help to assign an icon to represent the student in the application.
IconData	Controls the icon and register the information associated with it.
MapCtrl	Controls the interaction with the map that allows the user to enter to each area of the farm and with that to enter to each specific game in the platform
HttpRequest	It is the class that controls the link with the server and database. It is responsible for downloading and uploading the corresponding data from and to the database.

GAMES INTERFACE

All the games included in the platform have a user interface to allow the following functionalities:

- Select the level for that specific game.
- Enter the demonstration of the game or play it, depending on the child's needs.
- Read short instructions to know what the child has to do in the game.
- Skip the demonstration section if needed.
- Pause the game for any reason, giving the option to read the instructions again, change the settings for the game or exit the game.
- Give information about the performance in the game and the scores obtained.

The interface created uses the same design as the main interface to keep consistency in the style used for the game and immerse the child in a completely different world formed by the ecofarm and all its areas.

Each game has a different screen for each part (instructions, demonstrations...), but all of them have a similar style and content. We will describe all the screens using one of the games as an example, in this case, the Attention game played inside the forest near the farm.

The first interface for each game is the instructions screen. As you can see in the image, there is information about the levels for that game (in this case, three), a short text with instructions to describe the objective of the game and two buttons, play and demo. In this screen, the user can select the level in which he/she will play the game, read the information about the objectives, enter the demonstration part or start to play the game.

When the demo button is selected, the child enters the demonstration of the game, in which it is

possible to see step-by-step instructions for that specific game to allow the child to understand what he/she has to do inside the game. The methodology is clear. The child or the teacher reads each of the instructions, and, when it is clear, they can move to the next step by pressing the next button (>>). In some parts of the demonstration, the child has to interact with the elements in a similar way as they have to do inside the real game. This will allow a better understanding of the game's objectives, while interacting in a guided way with the demonstration.

It is possible to skip the demonstration when necessary by pressing the upper right button in the interface. A confirmation panel will be shown to confirm whether or not the child wants to skip the demonstration. This is done because the button can be pressed accidentally, and in that case, entering the demonstration again will start it from the beginning.

Each game has a different interaction method; some of them use the touch screen to select elements in the environment, others have buttons to indicate if it is correct or not the selection and others use a combination of both. Something common for all the games is the pause button, which is present in the game scenario while the child is playing. This button allows the child to pause the game for some reason: remembering the objectives, changing any setting in the game or exiting the game.

When the child presses the pause button, a specific pause menu is presented with different

options (see image below). If the Instructions or Settings button is pressed, there will be information or options to change the current settings, presented on a new screen. In both of them, it is possible to go back to the pause menu. Pressing the exit button will stop the game that was in progress and exit to the instructions screen. It is also possible to close the pause menu by pressing the X button in the upper right corner of the panel.

After playing a game, the interface shows a collection of data resulting from the child's performance. These variables are important to measure not only the child's performance in that game but also to extract important data to adapt the game to each specific user and review the progression in that task.

For this part of the interface, the game interface, the flowchart is:

The UML diagram will be included in the Game Module UML diagram, described in the next section.

GAME MODULE

The game module is the implementation of each game in the platform. All games share a base class where all the common attributes and functionalities are controlled, and a specific class for each game that derives from the base class, with specific content and the implementation of the functionalities specific to each of the games.

The flowchart for this part is:

And the UML diagram of classes is (see more detailed diagram in Annex 3 and Annex 5 for bigger size):

General class diagram

In this case, only the GameCtrl class has access to the server and database. With that, all its derived classes for the games can connect to the server to upload information about the results of the game. The attribute included in the GameCtrl is request, that is a Unity GameObject, and inside the code we access to the HTTPRequest script attached to this gameobject in the scene:

```

GameCtrl
+ type: ActivityType
+ instructionsPanel: GameObject
+ resultsPanel: GameObject
+ guiCamera: GameObject
+ sceneCamera: GameObject
+ gameSceneGroup: GameObject
+ uploadingImage: GameObject
+ correctSound: AudioSource
+ wrongSound: AudioSource
+ eyeTrackerCtrl: EyeTrackerCtrl
+ replayManager: ReplayManager
+ numTrials: int
+ numTestTrials: int
+ currentLevel: int
+ currentSubLevel: int
+ demoSequence: GameObject
+ endDemo = false
+ skipDemo = false
+ endTrial = false
+ inTrial = false
+ playButton: GameObject
+ pauseButton: GameObject
+ returnToInstructionsButton: GameObject
+ pausePanel: GameObject
+ countdown: GameObject
+ wellDonePanel: GameObject
+ nextRoundPanel: GameObject
+ request: GameObject
+ valueTotalCorrectAnswers: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueCorrectPresent: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueCorrectAbsent: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueTotalIncorrectAnswers: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueIncorrectPresent: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueIncorrectAbsent: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueCorrectPepperClassify: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueIncorrectPepperClassify: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueCorrectSelSort: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueCorrectSelNotSort: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueLongSequence: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueMeanRT: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueMeanRTPresent: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueMeanRTAbsent: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valuePercentTrialsNoAnswer: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueTotalTrials: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueTotalCategoryCorrectSort: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueTrialsForFirstCategory: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valuePerseverativeResponses: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueConceptualLevelResponses: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueLearningToLearn: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valuePervasiveErrors: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueNonPerseverativeErrors: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueFailureMaintainSet: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueWaitTimeTrial1: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueWaitTimeTrial2: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueWaitTimeTrial3: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueAbleToWaitTrial1: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueAbleToWaitTrial2: TextMeshProUGUI
+ valueAbleToWaitTrial3: TextMeshProUGUI
+ confirmPanel: GameObject
+ lastInteractionResult = 2
# hits = 0
# errors = 0
# errorAbsent = 0
# errorPresent = 0
# correctPresent = 0
# correctAbsent = 0
# correctPepperClassify: int
# incorrectPepperClassify: int
# correctSelSorting = 0
# correctSelNotSorting = 0
# longestSequence = 0
# meanRT = 0.0f
# meanRTPresent = 0.0f
# meanRTAbsent = 0.0f
# percentTrialsNoAnswer = 0.0f
# rPerTrial = new List<float>()
# totalNumTrials = 0
# numCategoryCorrectSort = 0
# numTrialsForFirstCategory = 0
# numPerseverativeResponses = 0
# numConceptualLevelResponses = 0
# numLearningToLearn = 0
# numPervasiveErrors = 0
# numNonPervasiveErrors = 0
# numFailureMaintainSet = 0
# waitTimeTrial1 = 0.0f
# waitTimeTrial2 = 0.0f
# waitTimeTrial3 = 0.0f
# ableToWaitTrial1 = false
# ableToWaitTrial2 = false
# ableToWaitTrial3 = false
- sessionIDdb: int
- activityIDdb: int
+ onFinished: UnityEvent
+ inPause = false

Start ()
Update ()
- Awake ()
- OnEnable ()
+ GoHome ()
+ <async> OnPressDemo ()
+ <async> OnPressPlay ()
+ SetupLevel ()
+ StartDemo (); Ienumerator
+ StartGame (); Ienumerator
+ PlayTest ()
+ ShowResults ()
+ <async> EndGame ()
+ ReturnToInstructionsScreen ()
+ GetHits (); int
+ GetErrors (); int
+ PauseGame (condition : bool)
+ getAbleToWaitTrial1 (); bool
+ AddInteractionEvent (start : bool)
    
```

```

HTTPRequests
+ apiUrl = "http://192.168.137.1:9000/api"
+ interfaceCtrl: interfaceCtrl
- currentUser: PostUser

+ OnEnable ()
+ addUser (user : User)
+ <async> addStudentSessionDoneDB (student : Student, session : Session)
+ <async> updateStudentDB (student : Student)
+ <async> addSensor_Status (sensorStatus : Sensor_Status, message : string): Task
+ <async> getLastSensorStatus (); Task
+ <async> addStudent (student : Student): Task
+ <async> updateStudent (student : Student): Task
+ <async> addUserStudent (teacherID : int, studentID : int): Task
+ <async> addEvent (eventid : int, type : EventType, data :EventData, timeStamp : long): Task
+ <async> addSessionActivity (sessionID : int, activityID : int); Task
+ <async> addStudentSessionDone (studentID : int, sessionID : int): Task
+ <async> addStudentSessionPlanned (studentID : int, sessionID : int): Task
+ <async> addActivityEvent (activityID : int, eventID : int): Task
+ <async> addRTPerTrialActivity (rPerTrialID : int, activityID : int): Task
+ <async> findUserDB (username : string): Task
+ <async> findStudentID (); Task
+ <async> getCurrentActivity (); Task
+ <async> getListStudentIDs (userID : int): Task
+ <async> getListSessionIDs (); Task
+ <async> getListRTPerTrialIDs (); Task
+ <async> getListEventIDs (); Task
+ <async> getListActivityIDs (); Task
+ <async> getStudentDB (id : int): Task
+ <async> getUserDB (id : int): Task
Post (user : User); Ienumerator
PostSessionCO (session : Session); Ienumerator
    
```

Class	Description
GameCtrl	It is the base class for all the games. It has all the variables shared between games and stored in the database, the common functions and access to each specific demonstration scene.
ForestGameCtrl	This class derives from GameCtrl and controls the attention game developed inside the forest near the farm.
PatchGameCtrl	This class derives from GameCtrl and controls the working memory game developed inside the farm's vegetable patch.
HouseGameCtrl	This class derives from GameCtrl and controls the inhibition game developed in the garden near the farm's house.
FarmGameCtrl	This class derives from GameCtrl and controls the cognitive flexibility game developed inside the farm's barn.
BeeFarmGameCtrl	This class derives from GameCtrl and controls the delayed gratification game developed in the bee farm.
MarketGameCtrl	This class derives from GameCtrl and controls the emotion naming game developed in the market.
DemoSequenceForestCtrl	It is the class that controls the demonstration for the attention game.
DemoSequenceVegPatchCtrl	It is the class that controls the demonstration for the working memory game.
DemoSequenceHouseCtrl	It is the class that controls the demonstration for the inhibition game.
DemoSequenceFarmCtrl	It is the class that controls the demonstration for the cognitive flexibility game.
DemosSequenceBeeFarmCtrl	It is the class that controls the demonstration for the delayed gratification game.

EyeTrackerCtrl	It is an intermediary class to link the games with the eye tracker API.
HttpRequest	It is the class that controls the link with the server and database. It is responsible for downloading and uploading the corresponding data from and to the database.
Other minor classes	These classes help to control the elements inside the games.

The most important part of this UML diagram for the game’s module is the main class GameCtrl and the derived classes for each game.

We implemented a global class GameCtrl that has all the important functionality needed for all

the games on the platform. We derived each of the specific game classes from that class, with more detailed functionality depending on the game objectives. This allows us to follow the same structure for all the games and keep a common baseline for the platform.

DATA RECORDER FOR REPLAY

All games have a module integrated to record each movement, action, interaction and change while the child is playing. This is like a recorder in real-time, with more functionalities than a simple recorded video. With the “replay” functionality is possible:

1. To check what happened in that game in a specific session after it was played.
2. It is possible to add data from the database later to get better information about what happened during the session. For instance, it is possible to load the wearable data from the database, match physiological data with events, actions, or interaction moments inside the game, and analyse the emotional state of the user in each moment. Also, it is possible to add specific functions to analyse in detail the situation and the conditions behind each answer, giving a powerful control of analysis of the session and games after they were played.
3. We can extract all the necessary data for the algorithms to feed them with real data from real sessions. This will help to train the algorithms to later obtain both offline and online answers from them to adapt the games or give the corresponding feedback to the teacher or professional about how to play the game with that specific user or which level is better for him/her.

Considering these functionalities, the replay module was developed and integrated into the game module to record all the specific data. The UML diagram is shown in the following image (see Annex 5 for bigger size):

General class diagram

In detail:

MouseFrame	It records information about the mouse interaction in each frame.
Other minor classes	They help to represent other information inside the replay module, needed for the functionality.

EYE-TRACKING MODULE

The eye-tracking module is integrated inside the games that can use this functionality to record where the child is looking. The selection of the games is based on the interaction methodology of the game, because all the games can be played using the touch screen, but this interaction is problematic for the eye tracker because the hand of the student covers totally or partially the field of view of the sensor. When the hand interacts with the touch screen, it enters in the area of vision of the eye tracker and that covers the user's face and eyes totally or partially. For that reason, the eye-tracking module is only integrated in games where the interaction is simple and can be controlled by a key in the keyboard or a button in the mouse.

The UML diagram for the eye-tracking module is the following (see Annex 5 for bigger size):

UML class diagram

And the API methods:

Name	Type	Description
Connect	Method	Sets up the connection to the Eye tracker device.
Disconnect	Method	Disposes the Eye tracker. Should be used when closing the game.

StartGazeDataCollection	Method	Starts the gaze data collection.
StopGazeDataCollection	Method	Stops the gaze data collection.
Save	Method	Saves the collected data to databases, CSV files and performs necessary calculations.
CreateConnection	Method	Creates the connection to the MariaDB.
SetActivity	Method	Sets the current activity, including UserID, GameID and SessionID.
GetLatestGazeData	Method	Returns the last collected GazeData that has been collected.
GetLatestFixationData	Method	Returns the last collected fixation data collected in the last 30 seconds.
GetPreviousInvalidGazeDataNumber	Method	Returns how many invalid gaze data were collected in the previous five seconds.
ClearInvalidGazeDataFromList	Method	Removes all invalid data from the memory list.
GetCurrentSessionID	Method	Returns the current Session ID.
GetCurrentActivityID	Method	Returns the current Activity ID.
RawGazeData	Property	Returns the raw gaze data generic list.
RecordingState	Property	Returns the recording state of the GazeDataProcessor.
SigthState	Property	Returns the current sight state based on the latest GazeData.
State	Property	Returns the state of the Eye Tracker device.
IsSaveRunning	Property	Indicates whether data saving is currently running or not.

In the last version of the platform, the ET module is accessible by all the games included in the platform. Despite the different interaction mechanism of each game and the possible loss of data, we considered that it was better to record as much data as possible from all the devices, included the eye-tracker to use it in the analysis done after the studies. If the eye-tracker was able to capture data while the child is thinking or deciding, that can help in the analysis to determine the attention pattern in each case.

#4. Wearable Module

The wearable module has been implemented using Kotlin programming language, targeting devices that are running Wear Operating System. The structure of the application can be seen in the UML diagram below, which showcases the following main components:

Component	Description
SensorValue	Encapsulates one reading from any of the device's sensors (accelerometer, PPG, gyroscope, etc.)
SensorData	Encapsulates all readings from a sensor, codified through the "type" property, for a specific time interval
SensorsData	Encapsulates all readings from all sensors for a specific time interval
DiscoverResponse	Codifies the answer of the server to the very first contact from the wearable. The answer is the same for both manual and automatic connection approaches. The "timestamp" value ensures that the server and wearable are synchronised.
DataPostResponse	Codifies the answer from the server after some data has been saved from the wearable (usually each second). The server sends back updated information about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the number of records saved in the database • the current session and activity • any errors encountered in the data saving process
StudentIdResponse	Codifies the answer from the server on searching the current student, either by ID or by nickname
API_CGIS_EMPOWER	Is the interface that describes in Kotlin language the API exposed by the server. All the communication between the wearable and the server is performed according to this description.

EmpowerConnectivityManager	Manages the WiFi connection states on the wearable. Due to the aggressive energy optimisation policies, the wearable WiFi connection is ON only when necessary. This component ensures that connectivity is available when the application tries to make any requests to the server.
NetworkActivity	Represents the first activity of the application, allowing the setup of the connection between the wearable and the server. It provides two ways for connection setup: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • manual – when the user inputs the IP of the server manually • automated – when the app scans the network in search of the server Connection is established only when: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. communication is possible 2. timestamp is aligned with a maximum difference of 2 seconds
StudentInfoActivity	Can be reached only after a successful connection is established with the server. Using this activity, the user connects all the sensor readings with a specific student. Note: as explained later in the document, there are mechanisms in place to automatically assign, on the server side, readings from the sensors to the active student. This approach was added after the first pilot when the necessity to display some minimum student information on the wearable has been noticed.
RecordingActivity	If the previous steps (wearable-server connection, student identity confirmation) have been completed successfully, the recording of the data from the sensors can be started. This component provides the necessary tools to coordinate the data recording process and displays important information about the student.
RecordingService	Performs the readings from all the sensors in real time, dealing with the restrictions imposed by the wearable operating system. The implementation approach is based on the concept of <code>ForegroundService</code> , which enables applications to access real-time sensor data for longer time intervals.
HeartRateListener	Connects to the PPG sensor readings and converts the custom values received in the <code>SensorData</code> representation.

AccelerometerListener	Connects to the Accelerometer sensor readings and converts the custom values received in the SensorData representation.
SensorsConnectionListener	Manages the components that connect to all the sensors for data reading. It starts and stops the recording process simultaneously on all sensors. This component is an inner class of the RecordingService.

The wearable module is also used in all the games included in the platform. Its functionality is the same in all the games, so the device just has to access to the database to check which is the game active in each moment and record all the data while the child is playing, storing it in the database associated with the corresponding game.

#5. Teacher Application

The teacher application is a tool developed in Unity for an Android mobile device, where the teacher can answer part of the questionnaires for the user needed in the tests before and after the games. Also, it is possible to control the state of the wearable and ET device and report real-time events that can happen during the session (changes in the emotional state of the child, changes in the behaviour, unexpected events, etc).

For that, we developed an easy interface to allow the teacher to do all these tasks during the session. The application is connected to the database installed in the laptop used for the games application, so he/she can use the same username and password created inside the game application. With that, it is possible to access the list of students created in the database, associated with that user, and register all the needed answers and real-time events during the session.

The UML diagram for the teacher app is the following (detailed version in Annex 4 and bigger size in Annex 5):

General class diagram part 1

General class diagram part 2

Class diagram in detail part 2

Class	Description
PersistentData	Class to control all the variables shared by different classes and scenes that need to persist along the application.
User	It is the teacher or professional who helps the children to enter the application, selects the games to play and controls the child interaction during the session.
Student	It is the child with neurodevelopmental disorders who plays the games.
Session	It is the collection of games or activities the child will play in a specific day and moment.
Activity	It is each of the games from the platform.
ActivityType	It is an enumeration with the types of activities.
ConditionType	It is an enumeration with a list of possible conditions for the child profile.
InterfaceCtrl	It is the main class to control all the interaction and screen changes inside the application interface.
HttpRequest	It is the class that controls the link with the server and database. It is responsible for downloading and uploading the corresponding data from and to the database.
Questionnaire	It is the class to represent each questionnaire included inside the application.
QuestionnaireData	It represents the data needed to create the questionnaire information inside the application.
Section	It is a class to represent each part of the questionnaires included in the application.
Question	It is a class to represent each question inside the questionnaire.
QuestionnaireResult	It represents the results of each questionnaire included.
QuestionnaireDataResultOnSession	It represents the results inside the questionnaire shown in the "on session" part.
SectionResultGame	It represents the results for each section for the game part.
SectionResult	It represents the results for each general section.
RealTimeEventsCtrl	It is a class to control the registration and upload to the database of real-time events.
SensorStatus	It is a class to get information from external devices (eye tracker and wearable) to inform

	the teacher about their status.
Other minor classes	They help to control and represent all the data in the application for its correct operation.

#6. MariaDB Database

All the components are connected to a MariaDB database. This database is installed locally in the laptop used for the tests, where the children play the games during the sessions. We have three main parts for the database: the games, the wearable, and the eye tracker data. Each part needs specific tables and attributes to store the needed information and data generated during the sessions. It is possible to see the guide to installing the server and mariaDB database in Annex 1.

GAMES DATABASE TABLES

The database stores all the variables for each game needed to measure the child's performance. It is because of that, we have information about the user (teacher or professional working with the kid), student (the child playing the games), session, activities and events.

The tables are the following (see Annex 5 for bigger size):

It is important to know that when the activity is running (the child is playing), we store certain events (for example, the start/end of the interaction in the activity) and also the teacher application sends to this database the real-time events that the teacher activates during the session. All are recorded in the table event related to the activity and timestamped. Also, we have special tables, for instance, the rtpertrialactivity, the response time for each trial in one activity. Inside the activity, we store the mean response time and also, in the specific table, the response time for each trial. Each time an activity is played, we create a register inside the database with all the corresponding measurements.

WEARABLES DATABASE TABLES

As can be seen in the System Architecture Diagram, the integration between the wearables module and the other parts of the system is implemented only through the database. This approach ensures that the components can be easily developed decoupled while all the data is integrated as a whole.

Data integration between the wearables and information from the other modules is showcased in the above diagram. As can be seen, each value recorded from the sensors is connected with:

- **student** - allows data recording for a student even if the session is not active (during breaks or while performing administrative tasks, etc.).
- **session** - ensures continuous data recording throughout the session, accounting also for the time between specific activities.
- **activity** - connects each activity with the sensor data recorded only while the participant performs the activity

Sensor status table ensures integration of the wearable module with the Teacher’s Application, providing real-time status information on how the wearable is performing (if there are recording issues, connection problems with the server, etc.).

EYE TRACKER DATABASE TABLES

The eye tracker module stores the values that are being registered while the child is interacting with specific games. These values are related to the position in the screen where the child is looking, pupil diameter, head position and validity of the data. Also, this module calculates some variables after the activity is finished, such as fixation duration, fixation position, saccade duration and velocity. All the data is timestamped to better match it with the other data inside the database (games and wearables).

IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_et`	IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_et_calc`	IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_et_state`	IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_status`
<pre>PK `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO INCREMENT `id_activity` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `id_session` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `PosX` float DEFAULT NULL `PosY` float DEFAULT NULL `PupilDiaX` float DEFAULT NULL `PupilDiaY` float DEFAULT NULL `HeadX` float DEFAULT NULL `HeadY` float DEFAULT NULL `HeadZ` float DEFAULT NULL `validity` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL `Timestamp` bigint(20) DEFAULT NULL</pre>	<pre>PK `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO INCREMENT `id_activity` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `id_session` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `fixation_starttime` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `fixation_duration` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `fixation_x` double DEFAULT NULL `fixation_y` double DEFAULT NULL `saccade_distance` double DEFAULT NULL `fixation_end` bigint(20) DEFAULT NULL `saccade_duration` int(11) DEFAULT NULL `saccade_velocity` double DEFAULT NULL `timestamp` bigint(20) DEFAULT NULL</pre>	<pre>PK `key` int(11) NOT NULL `device_state` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL `head_state_X` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL `head_state_Y` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL `head_state_Z` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL `gaze_state` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL</pre>	<pre>PK `id` tinyint(4) NOT NULL AUTO INCREMENT `wearable_status` tinyint(4) DEFAULT NULL `wearable_message` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL `wearable_timestamp` timestamp NULL DEFAULT NULL `et_status` tinyint(4) DEFAULT NULL `et_message` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL `et_timestamp` timestamp NULL DEFAULT NULL</pre>

The table for the sensor_status is used to connect and inform the teacher application about possible errors in the device and problems that need to be solved. As it is a device without any external indication about its status, the module added a method to check it regularly and feed the database with this information. With that, the Teacher Application can check this table and get the latest status and show it visually in the interface to keep the teacher informed (working well, stopped, invalid data...).

#7. Local Storage

The local storage is used mainly to record every step, interaction, answer and change in the game for the replay module. These files are json recorded in the local disk organised by user/student/activity folders. With that, we can reproduce exactly what happened in each activity during the session with a specific child. These files have all the information about the activity timestamped to allow reproduction of the activity and synchronisation with other data from the database. We can see some examples in the following code:

Information about a mushroom inside the attention game:

```
{
  "nombreObjeto": "Champi(Clone)_5",
  "nombrePadre": "",
  "isPrefabChild": false,
  "recordInstantiatedFrames": [
    1454
  ],
  "recordDeletedFrames": [
    0,
    1462
  ],
  "recordAnimationChanges": [],
  "recordSpriteChanges": [],
  "recordMaterialChanges": [],
  "frameList": [
    {
      "position": {
        "x": 966.56298828125,
        "y": 524.3740234375,
        "z": -4.6960000991821289
      },
      "scale": {
        "x": 2.0,
        "y": 2.0,
        "z": 2.0
      },
      "rotation": {
        "x": -0.7071068286895752,
        "y": 0.0,
        "z": 0.0,
        "w": 0.7071068286895752
      },
      "frameNum": 1455,
      "color": "#D6D6D6FF",
      "timestamp": 1704707817125,
    }
  ]
}
```

```
"audio": {  
  "playing": false,  
  "pitch": 0.0,  
  "volume": 0.0,  
  "panStereo": 0.0,  
  "spatialBlend": 0.0,  
  "reverbZoneMix": 0.0  
},  
"particleTime": 0.0  
}  
],  
"activeChilds": [],  
"instantiated": true  
}
```

Information about one of the distractors in the attention game:

```
{  
  "nombreObjeto": "FloresAmarillasMoradas(Clone)_2",  
  "nombrePadre": "",  
  "isPrefabChild": false,  
  "recordInstantiatedFrames": [  
    1532  
  ],  
  "recordDeletedFrames": [  
    0,  
    1539  
  ],  
  "recordAnimationChanges": [],  
  "recordSpriteChanges": [],  
  "recordMaterialChanges": [],  
  "frameList": [  
    {  
      "position": {  
        "x": 966.56298828125,  
        "y": 524.10797119140625,  
        "z": -4.6960000991821289  
      },  
      "scale": {  
        "x": 1.5,  
        "y": 1.5,  
        "z": 1.5  
      },  
      "rotation": {  
        "x": 0.0,  
        "y": 0.0,  
        "z": 0.0,  
        "w": 1.0  
      }  
    }  
  ]  
}
```

```
},  
"frameNum": 1533,  
"color": "#000000",  
"timestamp": 1704707824971,  
"audio": {  
  "playing": false,  
  "pitch": 0.0,  
  "volume": 0.0,  
  "panStereo": 0.0,  
  "spatialBlend": 0.0,  
  "reverbZoneMix": 0.0  
},  
"particleTime": 0.0  
}  
],  
"activeChilds": [  
  true,  
  true  
],  
"instantiated": true  
}
```


ANNEX 1

Installing and setting up the service

1. Premise

In this document we will look at what we need to install and how to set up the service so that we can run the server, connect our database and work with it.

Please follow the steps accordingly, as noted in this guide. For any further questions, please do not hesitate to ask

2. Installation and set up

2.1. Installing Node.js:

Go to <https://nodejs.org/en/blog/release/v18.16.0> and install Node.js v18.16.0.

In the installation wizard, choose the directory that stores the nodeJS files (can be left as default) and please make sure all the options are enabled, as shown in the figure below. There is no need to change the way the features will be installed:

When asked if we want to install tools for native modules, do not check that option since it is not necessary for our service.

2.2. Installing MariaDB:

Go to <https://mariadb.org/download> and install MariaDB version 10.11

In the installation wizard, choose the directory that will store the MariaDB files (can be left as default), and please make sure all the options are enabled as shown in the figure below. There is no need to change the way the features will be installed:

Now, we will work on configuring our database. We will set the password for our root user. We will be working with the password XXXXXXXX as a standard, so please enter that password in the password field.

In case we want to allow access to our database from remote machines (in our case, other

devices that will work with the data), please check the Enable access from remote machines for 'root' user option

Default instance properties
MariaDB 10.3 database configuration

MariaDB Server

Modify password for database user 'root'

New root password: Enter new root password

Confirm: Retype the password

Enable access from remote machines for 'root' user

Use UTF8 as default server's character set

Back Next Cancel

As for the rest of the settings, please make sure they are the same as in the figure below to ensure the expected performance of the database:

Default instance properties
MariaDB 10.11 (x64) database configuration

MariaDB Server

Install as service

Service Name:

Enable networking

TCP port:

InnoDB engine settings

Buffer pool size: MB

Page size: KB

Back Next Cancel

2.3. Setting up the database where the data will be stored

Now we need a database that the server will work with. We will work on our MySQLClient command window, which we can access by going to our Windows Start menu (located on the lower left corner of the Windows taskbar) and then typing MySQL client. Please make sure always to run the application with administrator rights (click on the Run as administrator button on the right or left click on it and press Run as administrator)

Once it shows up, we will click on it and the command prompt window will pop up.

We will authenticate ourselves by entering the password we set up before (XXXXXXX) and proceed with creating the empty database in which we will import our existing database. To do so we will enter the following command:

create database empowerdb;

* Please note that if the database is already created, or wants to be overwritten, this step can be skipped

Now we will close the MySQL Client command prompt window (it is important to make sure it is closed) and will open the Command Prompt window. To open it up, we will again go to

our Window Start menu and type Command prompt. Please make sure always to run the application with administrator rights as well.

We will now import the sql file data into the created empty database. To do so, we will use the following command:

```
mysql -u root -p empowerdb < C:\Project\EmpowerDBService\empowerdbnew.sql
```

Please make sure that the C:\ Project\EmpowerDBService \empowerdbnew.sql directory is where the sql file given is stored. This will vary depending on the device.

2.4. Setting up the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) and server files

We will need to create a project in our integrated development environment of choice so that we can run the files given (server.js, wroutes.js and route.js). In our case, we will be using Visual Studio Code.

We need to install the dependencies of the project that will be used to make the service work. We will now open our IDE terminal (which can be created by using the Terminal>New Terminal button in the Visual Studio Code taskbar)

We need to make sure that the terminal is located in the same directory as the files given (server.js, wroutes.js and routes.js) are. Please use the cd command to do so. Below is an

example:

```
cd Project/EmpowerDBService
```

Once we have made sure that we are in the correct location (hence no error has been produced) then we will input the following commands in our IDE and press the enter key:

```
npm init
```

We will now proceed with the installation of the necessary modules and packages for our server. Please enter the following commands, one by one, as one of them will install different utilities. Press the enter key after typing each one of them individually and wait for the dependencies to be installed:

```
npm install express  
npm install mysql express-myconnection  
npm install --save mysql2  
npm install cors
```

Below is an example of how the successful installation of one of the commands should look like

```
PS F:\Empower\Test> npm install express  
  
up to date, audited 82 packages in 650ms  
  
7 packages are looking for funding  
  run `npm fund` for details  
  
found 0 vulnerabilities  
PS F:\Empower\Test> █
```

Once this is completed, we will have now installed and set up all of the necessary files and settings.

3. Starting up the service

Once we are done with the installation and setup we will now proceed with starting up the service. Please note that this set must be performed whenever we want to use the service. We will open our IDE terminal (which can be created by using the Terminal>New Terminal button in the Visual Studio Code taskbar) as before

And we also need to make sure that the terminal is located in the same directory as the files given (server.js, wroutes.js and routes.js) are. Please use the `cd` command to do so. Below is the same example as before:

cd Project/EmpowerDBService

Once we have made sure that we are in the correct location (hence no error has been produced) we will run the project using the following command:

npm run start

If everything has been successful, we will get the following response in the terminal, which means the service is already running:

```
> empowermariadb@1.0.0 start
> node server.js

server running on port 9000
```

To double check this, we can open up our browser and enter localhost:9000 and we should be getting the following message:

Welcome to my API

ANNEX 2

Interface Diagrams:

This is a more in detail description of the classes used to implement the interface and its functionality inside the platform. It includes the C# classes, their relationship, the variables and functions controlled by each class. As the quantity of classes and their variables and functions are very big, we have split them in pieces to make them easily readable.

ANNEX 3

Games Diagram:

This is a more in detail description of the classes used to implement the games and their functionality inside the platform. It includes the C# classes, their relationship, the variables and functions controlled by each class. As the quantity of classes and their variables and functions are very big, we have split them in pieces to make them easily readable.


```

# waitTimeTrial1: float = 0.0f
# waitTimeTrial2: float = 0.0f
# waitTimeTrial3: float = 0.0f
# ableToWaitTrial1: bool = false
# ableToWaitTrial2: bool = false
# ableToWaitTrial3: bool = false
- sessionIDdb: int
- activityIDdb: int
+ onFinished: UnityEvent
+ inPause: bool = false

Start ()
Update ()
- Awake ()
- OnEnable ()
+ GoHome ()
+ «async» OnPressDemo ()
+ «async» OnPressPlay ()
+ SetupLevel ()
+ StartDemo (): IEnumerator
+ StartGame (): IEnumerator
+ PlayTest ()
+ ShowResults ()
«async» EndGame ()
+ ReturnToInstructionsScreen ()
+ GetHits (): int
+ GetErrors (): int
+ PauseGame (condition : bool)
+ getAbleToWaitTrial1 (): bool
+ AddInteractionEvent (start : bool)
    
```


ProductsCtrl
+ productGroup: Transform + productList: GameObject originalGroupScale: Vector3
Start () Update () - OnEnable () + enabledProducts (number : ProductNum)

ANNEX 4

Teacher APP Diagram:

This is a more in detail description of the classes used to implement the teacher app and its functionality inside the platform. It includes the C# classes, their relationship and the variables controlled by each class. As the quantity of classes and their variables and functions are very big, we have split them in pieces to make them easily readable.

SectionResultGame

```
+ «property» Name: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("Name")}
+ «property» Game: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("Game")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion1: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion1")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion2: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion2")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion3: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion3")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion4: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion4")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion5: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion5")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion6: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion6")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion7: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion7")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion8: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion8")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion9: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion9")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion10: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion10")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion11: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion11")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion12: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion12")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion13: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion13")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion14: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion14")}
+ «property» AnswerQuestion15: string
  {Annotation = XmlAttribute("AnswerQuestion15")}
```


InterfaceCtrl	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + introPanel: GameObject + loginPanel: GameObject + studentListPanel: GameObject + selectionScreen: GameObject + initEvaluationPanel: GameObject + initEvalExplanation: GameObject + initEvalQuestionnaire: GameObject + sessionEvaluation: GameObject + postSessionEvaluation: GameObject + questionnaireResult: QuestionnaireResult + toggleEnglish: Toggle + toggleRomanian: Toggle + togglePortuguese: Toggle + toggleSpanish: Toggle + username: TMP_InputField + password: TMP_InputField + listTextToChange: ChangeInterfaceLanguage + sectionTitle: TextMeshProUGUI + sectionInstructions: TextMeshProUGUI + questionsPerBlock: int = 4 + blockDataTitle: TextMeshProUGUI + sectionEF: GameObject + formQuestionsEF: QuestionOptionsCtrl + sectionSE: GameObject + formQuestionSE: QuestionOptionsCtrl + nextButtonForm: GameObject + gameSelected: string = "" + selectGame: GameObject + insideGameEventsPanel: GameObject + realTimeEventsPanel: GameObject + beforeGamePanel: GameObject + afterGamesPanel: GameObject + request: GameObject + afterSessionExplanation: GameObject + afterSessionQuestionnaire: GameObject 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + afterSessionQuestionnaire: GameObject + sectionASTitle: TextMeshProUGUI + sectionASInstructions: TextMeshProUGUI + sectionAS: GameObject + sectionASU: GameObject + formQuestionsAS: QuestionOptionsCtrl + nextButtonASForm: GameObject + asPart1: GameObject + asPart2: GameObject + errorText: TextMeshProUGUI nextButton: bool = false waitingForButton: bool = false getAllAnswers: bool = false totalAnswers: int = 0 currentQuestions: List<int> = new List<int>() formQuestions: QuestionOptionsCtrl usabilitySection: bool = false <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start () Update () - OnEnable () ViewIntroPanel (): IEnumerator + LanguageSelection (language : string) LoadQuestionnaire () + «async» OnLogin () + OnStart () + StartInitialEvaluation () QuestionnaireControl (): IEnumerator + StartAfterSessionEvaluation () QuestionnaireControlASU (): IEnumerator + StartAfterSessionEvaluationSecurity () QuestionnaireControlIASS (): IEnumerator + StartSessionEvaluation () + SelectGame (game : string) + StartGameEvaluation () + RealTimeEvaluation () + EndGameEvaluation () FillSectionData (s : Section) FillSectionDataAS (s : Section)

ANNEX 5

Class diagram in A3 size in order to see them completely in one screen. These are the diagrams included in the previous annexes but in an A3 size, to be able to see all the classes together and their relationship in a bigger format (that can fit all the classes together).

Interface Diagram Part 1

Interface Diagram Part 2

Games Diagram

Replay module class diagram

Teacher APP UML Diagram Part 2

MariaDB tables for Games module

MariaDB tables for Wearable Module

```

IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_et`
PK `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT
`id_activity` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`id_session` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`PosX` float DEFAULT NULL
`PosY` float DEFAULT NULL
`PupilDiaX` float DEFAULT NULL
`PupilDiaY` float DEFAULT NULL
`HeadX` float DEFAULT NULL
`HeadY` float DEFAULT NULL
`HeadZ` float DEFAULT NULL
`validity` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL
`Timestamp` bigint(20) DEFAULT NULL
    
```

```

IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_et_calc`
PK `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT
`id_activity` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`id_session` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`fixation_starttime` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`fixation_duration` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`fixation_x` double DEFAULT NULL
`fixation_y` double DEFAULT NULL
`saccade_distance` double DEFAULT NULL
`fixation_end` bigint(20) DEFAULT NULL
`saccade_duration` int(11) DEFAULT NULL
`saccade_velocity` double DEFAULT NULL
`timestamp` bigint(20) DEFAULT NULL
    
```

```

IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_et_state`
PK `key` int(11) NOT NULL
`device_state` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL
`head_state_X` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL
`head_state_Y` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL
`head_state_Z` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL
`gaze_state` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL
    
```

```

IF NOT EXISTS `sensor_status`
PK `id` tinyint(4) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT
`wearable_status` tinyint(4) DEFAULT NULL
`wearable_message` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL
`wearable_timestamp` timestamp NULL DEFAULT NULL
`et_status` tinyint(4) DEFAULT NULL
`et_message` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL
`et_timestamp` timestamp NULL DEFAULT NULL
    
```

MariaDB tables for ET Module